

Isolation and Identification of E-Coli from Infected Cases from Broilers Farms In 2019

Author's Details: Marwa. M. Khedr, May. F. Abdelaty and Mahmoud. M. Abotaleb

Central Laboratory for Evaluation of Veterinary Biologics, (CLEVB), Abbassia, Cairo, Egypt & Reference Laboratory of Quality control on Poultry Production, Animal Health Research Institute, Dokki, Giza, Egypt

Received Date: 08-Dec-2019

Accepted Date: 26-Dec-2019

Published Date: 31-Dec-2019

Abstract

E. coli infections are responsible for great economic loss and causing a serious threat to the poultry industry. One hundred and fifty samples were collected from different poultry farms for isolation of *E. coli* bacteria. Different percentage rates were 6%, 8.6% and 5.3 obtained from apparently healthy birds, freshly dead and diseased birds respectively. Thirty *E. coli* isolates were identified as (O1, O2, O6, O78 and O157). *E. coli* serotypes lethality tests in chicks showing clinical signs which appeared on the 5th day and the mortalities recorded at the 7th day post infection with percentage 7% of the challenged group. Lethality tests in mice showed mortality 100% at 3rd day post challenge in pathogenic serotypes. Molecular characterization was done for detection of *iss*, *ombA*, *fimH*, *iroN* and *pabC* virulence genes for *E. coli* serotypes. All isolates were positive for all genes except *papC* was negative. Antibiotic susceptibility test was applied for all for detection of the suitable antimicrobial agent in the infected poultry farms with *E. coli* in which all isolated serotypes were sensitive to ceftriaxone, tobramycin except O6 and were intermediate, with spectinomycin, amikacin and fosfomycin. Recently isolated serotypes may help in local vaccine production.

Key words: *E. coli*, pathogenicity, virulence genes, antibiotic

1. Introduction

Escherichia coli (*E. coli*) is considered as a member of the normal microflora of all warm-blooded animals including poultry (Kaper *et al.*, 2004). However, in the debilitated or in immune suppressed hosts, or when gastro-intestinal barriers are violated, even normal “non-pathogenic” strain of *E. coli* can cause infection to poultry, humans and animals. Moreover, there are certain *E. coli* strains designated as avian pathogenic *E. coli* which can cause localized or systemic infection outside the avian gut, which indicates as Extraintestinal Pathogenic *E. coli* (ExPEC). The infection caused by ExPEC is termed colibacillosis (Nakazato *et al.*, 2009) characterized by yolk sac infection, omphalitis, respiratory tract infection, septicemia, salpingitis and peritonitis affect broiler chickens aged 4–6 weeks as well as hazard economic impact in the infected birds’ productivity, high mortality, high cost condemnation of infected carcasses at slaughter, prophylaxis and treatment (Lutful *et al.*, 2010).

More than 1000 serotypes are known, but only a few are considered as important in avian pathology (Sojka and Carnaghan, 1961). Serotypes O1, O2, and O78 mostly stands behind the infection and represent 15-61% of the isolates, yet other types still exist (Dho-Moulin and Fairbrother, 1999) (Rahman *et al.*, 2004), therefore, Serotyping of potentially pathogenic *E. coli* strains is necessary to improve (Stordeur and Mainil, 2002). Pathogenic and non-pathogenic strains in poultry are differentiated based on virulence, which has been attributed to various genes (adhesion, invasins, toxins, resistance to host serum, iron acquisition systems, temperature-sensitive hemagglutinin, and K1 capsule) have all been shown to contribute to APEC pathogenesis (Alexander DJ and Senne DA, 2008). *fimH* gene is responsible for adhering to chicken epithelial cells of the pharynx and trachea by means of type 1 fimbriae, comprising a major structural subunit and *fimA* that mediates the attachment to d-mannose residues (Orndorff, 1994). Increased serum survival (*isS*) gene is known to be associated with serum resistance and is considered the most significantly associated gene with APEC strains

December 31, 2019

(Barbieri *et al.*, 2013) (Dissanayake *et al.*, 2014). P-fimbriae (papC) is important in the later stages of infection for the adhesion to internal organs (Dho and Fairbrother 1999).

Detection of pathogenic *E. coli* strains that cause septicemia becomes important for effective treatment with antimicrobial therapy and control resulting in reducing both the incidence and mortality which associated with colibacillosis (Dho *et al.*, 1990; Susantha *et al.*, 2001; Jeffrey *et al.*, 2002; Geornaraset *et al.*, 2004; Zhao *et al.*, 2009; Qabajah and Yaqoub. 2010) which is considered as challenging during its identification as pathogenic or nonpathogenic *E. coli* is a regular host of the digestive tract of poultry. The effective control of *E.coli* infection depended on suitable antimicrobial drugs due to the hazard use of antibiotics in humans and animals subsequently, has become the major factor for the emergence and spread of drug-resistance traits among pathogenic and commensal bacteria. The development of multi-drug resistance in *E.coli* is one of the major concerns worldwide (Von Baum and Marre. 2004). So, in this study, depending on the isolation of *E.coli* serotypes from different infected poultry farms in Cairo and Giza governorates for the detection pathogenic types by lethality test and PCR for further local vaccine production and detect the suitable antibiotic for the infected poultry in the infected farms.

2. Materials and Methods:

2.1. Samples:

One hundred and fifty samples were collected from apparently healthy birds (cloacal swabs), diseased birds (cloacal swabs) and freshly dead birds (liver, heart, spleen, lung and gall bladder samples) from suspected chickens with *E. coli* infection as shown in Table (1). The samples were transferred immediately to sterile buffered peptone water, then wrapped with ice, kept in a box and transferred directly into the lab which then isolated, characterized and serotyped in CLEVB (Central Laboratory for Evaluation of veterinary Biologics) and AHRI (Animal Health research institute).

Table 1: Sampling of examined organs samples

Source	Number of samples
Apparently healthy	60
Diseased	40
Freshly dead	50
Total	150

2.2 Preparation of sample:

The carcasses were promptly necropsied according to the standard procedures described by (Lowenstin. 1986). About 25 g of each were collected from the internal portion aseptically in a sterile plastic bag (Falconpack, UAE). Samples were kept at + 4 °C for a maximum of 24 until culturing.

2.3 Reference *E.coli* strain

E.Coli ATCC 25922 (AHRI) was used as a positive control strain and *E.coli* reference antisera 295347 Lot 473096.

2.4 Isolation and identification of *E. coli*:

a) Bacteriological methods

A loopful of the culture suspension was streaked on to MacConkey agar (Lab M, Neogen Europe Lt) and incubated sample for 24 h at 37 °C aerobically. Isolation of *E. coli* was performed according to (Quinn *et al.*, 2002).

b) Biochemical test:

Suspected *E. coli* colonies were then transferred onto nutrient agar for further identification using biochemical tests. The serotypes were subjected to an API 20E identification system (Kwon *et al.*, 2008).

c) The VITEK 2 automated system (bioMérieux): was used for confirmation of putative *E.coli* isolates (Espinar *et al.*, 2011).

d) Serological identification

E. coli isolates were serologically identified using rapid diagnostic *E. coli* antisera Set 1 containing polyvalent and monovalent O antisera (DENKA SEIKEN Co. LTD, Japan) according to (Edwards and Ewing. 1972).

2.5 In vitro lethality test of *E.coli* strains:

December 31, 2019

A-Lethality of *E. coli* isolates in day-old SPF chicks (Vidotto *et al.*, 1990):

Unvaccinated two day-old SPF chicks (8 chicks / serotype) obtained from El- Fayuim farm were used, which challenged orally with 0.5 ml containing 9.0×10^8 CFU/ml. Daily monitoring of clinical Signs, postmortem lesion of the inoculated serotypes for 7days post inoculation and monitored daily.

B-Lethality of *E.coli* isolates in Mice (Wyatt *et al.*, 2003):

Female swiss mice (8th to 10th weeks of age) were housed in micro-isolator cages and provided with food and water ad libitum. Mice were lightly anesthetized with Metofane (methoxyfluorane) (Schering-Plough Animal Health Co., Union, N.J.) in a glass desiccator and challenged with 0.2 ml of *E.coli* culture containing 1×10^9 CFU in order to measure morbidity and mortality. Control mice were inoculated with 0.2ml of the PBS diluents.

2.6 Detection of virulence genes for pathogenic *E.coli* isolates:

The DNA extraction was performed using the QIAamp DNA Minikit (Qiagen, Germany, GmbH) with modification from the manufacture's recommendations.

Oligonucleotide Primer: Primers used were supplied from Metabion (Germany) are listed in Table (2).

PCR amplification: Primers were utilized in a 25- μ l reaction containing 12.5 μ l of Emerald Amp Max PCR Master Mix (Takara, Japan), 1 μ l of each primer of 20 pmol concentrations, 4.5 μ l of water, and 6 μ l of DNA template. The reaction was performed in an applied biosystem 2720 thermal cycler.

Table 2: Primers sequences, target genes, amplicon sizes and cycling conditions

Primer designation	Primer Denaturation	Amplification (35 cycles)			Final Extension	Primers sequences 5' ---3'	Product	Reference
		Sequence denaturation	Annealing	Extension				
<i>Issgene</i>	94°C/5min	94°C /5min	54°C/30sec	72°C/30sec	72°C/7min.	F. ATGTTATTTTCTGCCGCTCTG R. CTATTGTGAGCAATATACCC	266bp	Yaguchi, et al., (2007)
<i>ompA gene</i>	94°C/5min	94°C/30 sec.	58°C/1min	72°C/1 min	72°C/10min	F. AGCTATCGCGATTGCAGTG R. GGTGTTGCCAGTAACCGG	919bp	Ewers et al., (2007)
<i>iroN gene</i>	95°C/5min	94°C/30sec	50°C/40sec	72°C/50sec	72°C/10min	F. ATCCTCTGGTCGCTAACT R. CTGCACTGGAAGAAGCTGTTCT	847bp	Ewers et al., (2007)
<i>fimH gene</i>	95°C/5min	94°C/30sec	50°C/40sec	72C/45sec	72°C/10min	F. GCAGAACGGATAAGCCGTGG R. GCAGTCACCTGCCCTCCGGTA	508bp	Ghanbar and Salehi. (2010)
<i>papC gene</i>	94°C/5min	94°C/30sec	50°C/40sec	72°C/45sec	72°C/10min	F. TGATATCACGCAGTCAGTAGC R. CCGGCCATATTCACATAA	501bp	Wen-jieet al., (2008)

2.7Antimicrobial susceptibility test:

The antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E.coli* isolates was conducted using the Kirby- Bauer disc diffusion method on Mueller-Hinton agar (Lab M, Neogen Europe Lt) according to the guidelines of the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute.(*CLSI/NCCLS. 2009*). the antimicrobials and their concentrations used for the susceptibility testing were listed in the table (3)

Table 3: The antimicrobials and their concentrations used for the susceptibility testing:

Test group	Antimicrobial agent	Disk content	Zone diameter nearest whole mm		
			Resistant	Intermediate	Sensitive
Aminoglycosides	Tobramycin (TOB10)	10 μ g	≤ 12	12-14	≥ 15
	Amikacin (AK30)	30 μ g	≤ 14	15-16	≥ 17
Tetracyclines	Oxytetracycline (TE30)	30 μ g	≤ 11	12-14	≥ 15
Fluoroquinolones	Ciprofloxacin (CIP5)	5 μ g	≤ 15	16-20	≥ 21
	Levofloxacin (LEV5)	5 μ g	≤ 13	14-16	≥ 17
Penicillins	Penicillin	10 μ g	≤ 10	-	≥ 28
	Ampicillin AMP10	10 μ g	≤ 13	14-16	≥ 17

December 31, 2019

Cephalosporins	Ceftriaxone	30µg	≤13	14-20	≥21
Folate pathway inhibitors	Trimethoprim+sulfamethoxazole SXT	1.25-23.75Mg	≤10	11-15	≥16
	Clindamycin DA	2 µg	≤14	15-20	≥21
Fosfomycins	Fosfomycin	200 µg	≤12	13-15	≥16
Quinolones	Nalidixic acid	30 µg	≤13	14-18	≥19
	Spectinomycin	10 µg	≤12	13-14	≥15
	Enrofloxacin	10 µg	≤12	13-16	≥17

3. Results:

3.1 Results of isolation and characterization:

As shown in table (4): A total of 30 suspected *E.coli* isolates were Gram negative, lactose fermenter on MacConkey, showed greenish metallic sheen on eosin methylene blue agar. On Nutrient agar medium showed Rounded, non-pigmented colonies, while on MacConkey agar medium appeared rounded, non-mucoid pink colonies (lactose fermenter) on the surface of the medium. The same isolates on Eosin Methylene blue (EMB) agar showed a distinctive yellow, green metallic.

Depending on the results of the API 20E identification system, the suspected *E. coli* isolates were 30 out of 150 suspected cases. The isolates gave positive reactions with ONPG, LDC, ODC, IND, GLU, MAN, SOR, RHA, SAC, MEL and ARA tests and negative reaction with ADH, CIT, H2S, URE, TDA, VP, GEL, INO, AMY and OX tests. Based on data revealed from The VITEK 2 automated system (bioMérieux). The thirty isolates were confirmed to be *E.coli*.

Table 4: Incidence of *E.coli* in the examined organs samples

Source	Number of examined organ samples	Number of positive samples
Apparently healthy	60	9(6%)
Diseased	40	13(8.6%)
Freshly dead	50	8(5.3%)
Total	150	30(20%)

The thirty suspected isolates that biochemically themorphological identified as *E. coli* which was classified into different serotypes using polyvalent and monovalent using standard antisera. The data revealed from the table (5), showed different serotypes (O1, O2, O6, O78 and O157) were (6, 6, 5, 9 and 4 isolates) were belonged to (O1, O2, O6, O78 and O157), respectively.

Table 5: Results of the serotyping of isolation *E.coli*.

Serotypes	No. of serotypes	percentage
O1	6	20%
O2	6	20%
O6	5	16.6%
O78	9	30%
O157	4	13.3%

3.3. Results of lethality test:

A- in chicks:

Clinical signs appeared by 5-day post infection in the infected group. These signs were dullness, depression, dropping of wings, off food, ruffled feather and inability to stand and gradually developed to brown diarrhea and gasping. Mortalities recorded at 7th day post-infection in the infected chicks which were (7%). Upon necropsy of died or sacrificed, birds congestion of liver, lung, spleen and kidneys and the 2 ceca filled with yellowish to greenish or brownish contents with gas. Later on, severe pericarditis, perihepatitis and gas distended ceca were observed.

B- in mice:

Mice mortalities were 100% at day 3 post inoculation.

3.4. Detection of virulence genes for pathogenic *E.coli* isolates:

December 31, 2019

Samples were confirmed for the presence of virulence genes (*iss* gene, *ompA* gene, *fimH* gene, *iroN* gene and *papC* gene) based on conventional RT-PCR assay. The conventional PCR assay was able to detect *iss*, *ompA*, *fimH*, *iroN* except *papC* virulence genes was negative for *E.coli* serotypes, as shown in table (6) and figures (1,2,3,4 and 5).

Table 6: PCR amplifications of *E .coli* serotypes:

Sample	<i>Iss</i> gene	<i>ompA</i> gene	<i>fimH</i> gene	<i>iroN</i> gene	<i>papC</i> gene
1	+	+	+	+	-
2	+	+	+	+	-
3	+	+	+	+	-
4	+	+	+	+	-
5	+	+	+	+	-
Amplicon size	266pb	919bp	508bp	847bp	501pb

Figure 1: The *iss* gene was detected in the five *E.coli* serogroups giving a positive PCR product of 266 bp

Figure 2: The *ompA* gene was detected in the five *E.coli* serogroups giving a positive PCR product of 919 bp

Figure 1: The *fimH* gene was detected in the five *E.coli* serogroups giving a positive PCR product of 508 bp

Figure 4: The *PapC* gene was amplified in the five *E.coli* serogroups giving a negative PCR product of 501 bp

Figure 4: The *iroN* gene was amplified in the five *E.coli* serogroups giving a negative PCR product of 847 bp

1:O1 2:O2 3:O6 4:O78 5:O157 Neg: negative control Pos: positive control L: Marker

December 31, 2019

5 Results of antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. coli* isolates:

The results of antimicrobial susceptibility test in table (7) showed that there was variation in the susceptibility of *E. coli* serotypes to the antibiotics drugs revealed high sensitivity percent (100%) to ceftriaxone, amikacin, fosfomicin and spectinomycin followed by tobramycin, trimethoprim, sulfamethoxazole and nalidixic acid revealed susceptibility (80%) then oxytetracycline, ciprofloxacin, levofloxacin, ampicillin, enrofloxacin (60%) and complete resistance was observed to clindamycin and penicillin (0%).

Table 7: antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. coli* isolates

Test group	Antimicrobial agent	<i>E. coli</i> pathogenic serotypes					Sen. %
		O1	O2	O6	O78	O157	
Cephems	Ceftriaxone	(S)	(S)	(S)	(S)	(S)	100%
Aminoglycosides	Tobramycin (TOB10)	(S)	(S)	(I)	(S)	(S)	80%
	Amikacin (AK30)	(S)	(S)	(S)	(S)	(S)	100%
Tetracyclines	Oxytetracycline (TE30)	(S)	(S)	(R)	(R)	(S)	60%
Fluoroquinolones	Ciprofloxacin (CIP5)	(R)	(S)	(R)	(S)	(S)	60%
	Levofloxacin (LEV 5)	(R)	(S)	(R)	(S)	(S)	60%
Penicillins	Penicillin	(R)	(R)	(R)	(R)	(R)	0%
	Ampicillin AMP10	(S)	(S)	(R)	(R)	(S)	60%
Folate pathway inhibitors	Trimethoprim+sulfamethoxazole	(S)	(S)	(S)	(R)	(S)	80%
	Clindamycin DA	(R)	(R)	(R)	(R)	(R)	0%
Fosfmycins	Fosfomicin	(S)	(S)	(S)	(S)	(S)	100%
Quinolones	Nalidixic acid	(S)	(S)	(I)	(S)	(S)	80%
	Spectinomycin	(S)	(S)	(S)	(S)	(S)	100%
	Enrofloxacin	(R)	(S)	(R)	(S)	(S)	60%

Sen: Sensitivity percent

S: Sensitive reaction

I: Intermediate reaction

R: Resistant reaction

4. Discussion

E. coli infection in poultry remains of great concern due to the impact in the poultry industry and public health sectors. Therefore evaluation of virulence and antibiotic resistance determinants is essential for predicting preventive measures.

The obtained results in the current study showed that on examination of 150 chicken samples, *E. coli* species were isolated with an overall percentage of 20% (Table 4). The highest isolation rate of Salmonella species was in apparently healthy birds (6%) followed by diseased birds (5.3%) and freshly dead (3.6%). This finding was almost in agreement with the report of (Dashe *et al.*, 2003). *E. coli* isolated from samples collected from infected hearts, lungs, air sacs, liver, spleen, ovaries, kidney, oviduct, intestine and bursa of fabricious by (Osman *et al.*, 1989).

The chicken embryo lethality assay (ELA) is a relatively simple and inexpensive test to predict virulence through the death of embryos (Seo *et al.*, 2013). Using the lethality system, clinical signs which appeared on the

December 31, 2019

fifth day after infection and the mortalities recorded at the 7th day post infection within one bird with a percentage 7% in the *challenged* group these signs similar to the general signs of *E. coli* infection recorded by (Awaad, 1972). *E. coli* isolates lethality in Mice showed mortality 100% at day 3 post challenged and this results similar to the results recorded by (Wyatt et al., 2003).

Several virulence determinants have been reported in different *E. coli* serovars. The distribution of seven virulence genes that play an important role in Salmonella for invasion, enterotoxin production and pathogenesis in the host were investigated.

iss gene that is known to be associated with serum resistance was found in 100% of the examined isolates. This finding is in conformity with that recorded by the result obtained by (Ewers et al., 2004) and (Moemen et al., 2014) showed a high incidence of the *iss* virulence gene as 82.7%, 73.8% respectively. Also, (rochal et al., 2008) (Wen-jie et al., 2008) and (Yaguchi et al., 2007) recorded similar results.

All of the examined isolates were positive for the *OmpA* gene and this result matches the result detected by (Mahmoud et al., 2018) and (Ewers et al., 2007) who isolated the *OmpA* gene from *E. coli* serotypes O2, O26, O78, O127, O1 and O91.

The *iroN* gene that is responsible for iron acquisition systems was found in all serotypes and this result like the result proved by (Carli et al., 2015) that demonstrated a high frequency of the bacterial genes *cvaC*, *iroN*, *iss*, *iutA*, *sitA*, *tsh*, *fyuA*, *irp-2*, *ompT* and *hlyF* in pathogenic strains and similar to the result showed by (Ewers et al., 2007).

The *fimH* virulence factor is seemed to be an essential unit for protecting the APEC isolates against the host immune system (Mellata 2013). In the present study, *fimH* gene was present in all the examined serotypes and this result like the result proved by (Akbar et al., 2018) who said That the prevalence of type 1 fimbrial adhesion gene (*fimH*) in APEC isolates was 66.66% and similar to the results showed by (Ghanbar and Salehi 2010). Another study has shown a higher prevalence of the *fimH* virulence gene (Ragione 2002).

P-fimbriae (*pap*) is important in the later stages of infection for the adhesion to internal organs was not detected in all examined serotypes. Other reports have also revealed the prevalence of the *Papc* gene, with a percentage of 24.3% (rochal 2008).

Regarding antibiogram of Salmonella isolates, the obtained results showed that 100% of the isolates were susceptible to ceftriaxone, amikacin, fosfomicin and spectinomycin followed by tobramycin, trimethoprim, sulfamethoxazole and nalidixic acid revealed susceptibility (80%) then oxytetracyclin, ciprofloxacin, levofloxacin, ampicillin, enrofloxacin was (60%). while high resistance rates were observed against clindamycin and penicillin. The results of the current study are nearly similar to the results obtained by (Zehor et al., 2017) which showed high level of resistance to tetracyclines (94.12%), sulfamethoxazole-trimethoprim (88.89%), enrofloxacin (86.27%), nalidixic acid (85.62%) and all the strains were susceptible to cefotaxime, excepting three, These findings were in close agreement with the results of (Shecho et al., 2017) who reported 100 and 92.3% susceptibility of *E. coli* isolates to ciprofloxacin and sulfamethoxazole-trimethoprim, respectively in Ethiopia (Edilu et al., 2019) showed that *E. coli* isolates were completely (100%) susceptible to ciprofloxacin, norfloxacin and sulfamethoxazole-trimethoprim and majority of the isolates were also susceptible to gentamicin (93%), streptomycin (85%), nalidixic acid (83%), kanamycin (75%).

Conclusions

The present study designed to isolate pathogenic *E. coli* strains from the infected farms which will be used after that for preparing the local vaccines for controlling *E. coli* infection in infected farms. One approach to the accurate determination of the pathogenic potential (pathotype) of isolated *E. coli* strains would be through a complete assessment of each strain for the presence of all known *E. coli* virulence genes by PCR to differentiate the (APEC) from (AFEC). The application of antibiotic susceptibility test for prevention of antimicrobial resistance associated with inappropriate use of antimicrobial drugs in humans and animals has been the major factor for the emergence and spread of drug-resistance traits among pathogenic and commensal bacteria which became of major concern worldwide Therefore, control of irrational use of antimicrobial in humans and farm

animals including limiting the availability of antimicrobials in the illegal market needs to be addressed. Moreover, the establishment of guidelines for prudent use of antimicrobials in farm animals with effective enforcement is required in Egypt.

6. References:

- i. **Alexander DJ and Senne DA.(2008):** *Newcastle disease, other avian paramyxoviruses and Pneumovirus infections. Diseases of poultry.*
- ii. **Akbar, A., Taghi, Z.,Mahmoud, J and Reza, G. (2018):** *ECOR phylotyping and determination of virulence genes in Escherichia coli isolates from pathological conditions of broiler chickens in poultry slaughter-houses of southeast of Iran. Vet Res Forum. 9(3): 211–216.*
- iii. **Ammar A.M, El-Hamid M.I, Eid S.E.A, El Oksh A.S.(2015):** *Insight into antimicrobial resistance and virulence genes of emergent multidrug resistant avian pathogenic Escherichia coli in Egypt:How closely related are they? Rev. Med. Vet. 2015;166(9-10):304–314.*
- iv. **Awaad M.H. (1972):***Studies on E. coli Infection in Chickens: M. V. Sc. Thesis, Fac. Vet. Med., Cairo Univ., Egypt.*
- v. **Barbieri N. L., de Oliveira A. L., Tejkowski T. M., Pavanelo D. B., Rocha D. A., Matter L. B., Callegari-Jacques S. M., de Brito B. G. and Horn F.(2013):***Genotypes and pathogenicity of cellulitis isolates reveal traits that modulate APEC virulence. PLoS ONE. 8(8) doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0072322.e72322.*
- vi. **Carli, S., Ikuta, N., Lehmann, FK., da Silveira, VP., de MeloPredebon, G., Fonseca, AS. and Lunge, VR. (2015):** *Virulence gene content in Escherichia coli isolates from poultry flocks with clinical signs of colibacillosis in Brazil. Poult Sci. 94(11):2635-40.*
- vii. **CLSI/NCCIS (2009):** *Performance Standards for Antimicrobial Disk Susceptibility Tests; Approval Standard-Tenth Edition and Performance Standards for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Test; M02-A10 and M100-S20. Published online 2017 Jul 28. doi: 10.14202/vetworld.2017.830-835.*
- viii. **Dashe, Y., Raji, M., Abdu,PandOladele B. (2003):** *Distribution of aerobic bacteria in visceral organs of sick and apparently healthy chickens in Jos, Nigeria. Int Res J Microbiol. 4:79–83.*
- ix. **Dho-Moulin M. and Fairbrother J. M. (1999):** *Avian pathogenic Escherichia coli (APEC) Veterinary Research. 30(2-3):299–316.*
- x. **Dho, M., Vandenboseh, J. F., Girardeau, J. P., Bree, A., Barat, T. and Lafont, J. P. (1990):** *Surface antigens from E. coli O2, and O78 strains. Infect. Immun., 58: 740-745.*
- xi. **Dissanayake D. R., Octavia S. and Lan R. (2014):** *Population structure and virulence content of avian pathogenic Escherichia coli isolated from outbreaks in Sri Lanka. Veterinar Microbiology. 31(168):403–412.*
- xii. **Edilu, J.,Kebede, A.,Morka, D.,Endrias, Z.,Bizunesh, M. ,and Ayichew, T. (2019):** *Identification and antimicrobial susceptibility profile of Escherichia coli isolated from backyard chicken in and around ambo, Central Ethiopia. BMC Vet Res.15: 85.*
- xiii. **Edwards, R. and Ewing, H. (1972)** *Identification of Enterobacteriaceae. Burgess Publishing Co., Minneapolis. p709.*
- xiv. **Espinar, M., Rocha, R., Ribeiro, M., Gonçalves,R.,and Pina-Vaz C.(2011):** *Extended-spectrum β -lactamases of Escherichia coli and Klebsiellapneumoniae screened by the VITEK 2 system. J Med Microbiol. 60(Pt 6):756-60.*

- xv. **El-Sukhon SN, Musa A and Al-Attar M.(2002):** *Studies on the bacterial etiology of airsacculitis of broilers in northern and middle Jordan with special reference to Escherichia coli, Ornithobacteriumrhinotracheale, and Bordetella avium.* Avian Dis. 46(3):605–12.
- xvi. **Ewers, C.;Li, G.; Wilking, H.; Kiebling, S.; Alt, K.; Antao, E.M.; Laturnus, C.; Diehl, I.; Glogge, S.; Homeier, T.; Bohnke, U.; Steinruck, H.; Philipp, H.c.andWieler, L.h. (2007):** Avian pathogenic, uropathogenic, and newborn meningitis-causing *Escherichia coli*: how closely related are they? *International Journal of Medical Microbiology* .Volume 297, Issue 3, 11 June 20.
- xvii. **GamalYounis, AmalAwad, and Nada Mohamed (2017):** Phenotypic and genotypic characterization of antimicrobial susceptibility of avian pathogenic *Escherichia coli* isolated from broiler chickens. *Vet World*. 2017 Oct; 10(10): 1167–1172. doi: 10.14202/vetworld.2017.1167-1172.
- xviii. **Geornaras, I., Hastings, J.W., and Holy, A. (2004):** Genotypic analysis of *Escherichia coli* strains from poultry carcasses and their susceptibilities to antimicrobial agents. *Applied Environmental Microbiol.* 67: 1940-1944.07, Pages 163-176.
- xix. **Ghanbarpour and Salehi (2010):** Determination of Adhesion Encoding Genes of Uropathogenic in *Escherichia coli* isolates from omphalitis of chicks. *American of Animal and veterinary sciences* 5(2): 91-96.
- xx. **Jeffrey, J.S., Nolan, K. H., Tonooka, S., Wolfe, W., Giddings, S. M., Horne, S. L., Foley, A. M., Lynne, J. O., Ebert L. M., Elijah, G., Bjorklund, S., Pfaff- McDonough, J., Singer, R. S., and Doetkott, C. (2002):** Virulence factors of *Escherichia coli* from Cellulitis or Colisepticemia lesions in chickens. *Avian Diseases*, 46: 48-52.
- xxi. **Kaper, JB., Nataro, JP. and Mobley HL(2004):.** Pathogenic *Escherichia coli*. *Nat Rev Microbiol.* 2:123–140.
- xxii. **Kwon, S. G.; Cha, S. Y.; Choi, E. J.; Kim, B.; Song, H. J. and Jang, H. K. (2008):** Epidemiological prevalence of avian pathogenic *E. coli* differentiated by multiplex PCR from commercial chickens and hatchery in Korea. *J. Bacteriology and Virology.* 38(4): 179-188.
- xxiii. **Lowenstine, L. (1986):** Necropsy procedures. In: Harrison LR, editor. *Clinical avian medicine and surgery.* W. B. Saunders; p. 298–309.
- xxiv. **Lutful, KS. (2010):** Avian Colibacillosis and Salmonellosis: a closer look at epidemiology, pathogenesis, diagnosis, control and public health concerns. *Int J Environ Res Publi Health.* 7:89–114.
- xxv. **Mahmoud,A., Ghada, M., Amgad, A. and Abeer, M. (2018):** Serotyping and Virulence Genes Detection in *Escherichia coli* Isolated from Broiler Chickens.jbs.vol.18 no.1.2018.p.46-50.
- xxvi. **Mellata M. (2013):** Human and avian extra-intestinal pathogenic *Escherichia coli*: Infections, zoonotic risks, and antibiotic resistance trends. *Foodborne PathogDis.*10(11):916–932.
- xxvii. **Moemen, A. M, Mostafa, A. S. and Elshimaa, R(2014):** Virulence Genes Content and Antimicrobial Resistance in *Escherichia coli* from Broiler Chickens. *Vet Med Int.* 2014; 2014: 195189.
- xxviii. **Mude, S., Naod, T., Jelalu, K., and Yimer, M. (2017):** Cloacael Carriage and Multidrug Resistance *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 from Poultry Farms, Eastern Ethiopia. *J Vet Med.* . doi: 10.1155/2017/8264583.
- xxix. **Nakazato, G., Tatiana, A., Eliana, G., Marcelo, B. and Wanderley, D.(2009):** Virulence factors of avian pathogenic *Escherichia coli* Pesq. *Vet Bras.* 29:479–486.
- xxx. **Orndorff, P. E. (1994):** *Escherichia coli* type 1 pili, p. 91-111. In V. L. Miller, J. B. Kaper, D. A. Portnoy, and R. R. Isberg (ed.), *Molecular genetics of bacterial pathogenesis.* ASM, Washington, D.C.
- xxxi. **Osman, E., Osman, K., Mehmet, C. and Ersin, I. (1989):** Haem-agglutination, Hydrophobicity, Enterotoxigenicity and Drug-Resistance characteristics of avian *E. coli*. *Avian diseases* 33: 631-635.
- xxxii. **Qabajah, L., and Yaqoub, A. (2010):** Identification and Screening of Avian Pathogenic *E.coli* Virulence Factors in Palestine. *Biotechnology Research Center, Palestine Polytechnic University, P.O-Box 198, Hebron, Palestine.*

December 31, 2019

- xxxiii. **Ragione, Rand Woodward, M. (2002):** Virulence factors of *Escherichia coli* serotypes associated with avian coli septicaemia. *Res Vet Sci.* 2002;73:27–35.
- xxxiv. **Rahman.M.,Samad, M., Rahman, J. and andKabir, S.(2004):** Bacterio-pathological studies on salmonellosis, colibacillosis and pasteurellosis in natural and experimental infections in chickens. *Bangladesh J Vet Med.* 2:1–8.
- xxxv. **Rocha, A., Rocha, S., Lima-Rosa, C., Souza, G.,Moraes, H., Salle, F.,Moraes, L. and Salle, Carlos T.P. (2008):** Genes associated with pathogenicity of avian *Escherichia coli* (APEC) isolated from respiratory cases of poultry. *Bras. vol.28 no.3 Rio de Janeiro.*
- xxxvi. **Rodriguez-Siek K. E, Giddings C. W., Doetkott C., Johnson T. J., and Nolan L. K. (2005):** Characterizing the APEC pathotype. *Vet. Res.*36: 214:256.
- xxxvii. **Salama, S. S; Afaf A. K.; Elham A. E. and Taha, M. M. (2007):** Molecular Strategies for the differentiation and identification of local *E. coli* isolated from chicken: I. characterization of protein profile. *B.S. Vet. Med. J. January, 17 (1):* 25-28.
- xxxviii. **Shecho, M., Thomas, N., Kemal, J. and Muktar, Y. (2017):** Cloacael carriage and multidrug resistance *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 from poultry farms, eastern Ethiopia. *J Vet Med.* 2017. 10.1155/2017/8264583.
- xxxix. **Susantha, M. G., Riddell, C., Andrew, A. P., and Allan, B. J. (2001):** Phenotypic and genotypic characterization of virulence factors of *Escherichia coli* isolated from broiler chickens with simultaneous occurrence of cellulitis and other colibacillosis lesions. *Canadian J. Vet.Res.,* 65: 1 -6.
- xl. **Sojka, W.J. and Carnaghan, R.B.A. (1961):** *Escherichia coli* infection in poultry. *Res. Vet. Sci.,* 2: 340-352.
- xli. **Stordeur, P. and Mainil, J. (2002):** Avian colibacillosis. *Ann. Med. Vet.,* 146: 11-18.175
- xlvi. **Vidotto, M.C., Muller, E.E., de Freitas, J.C., Alfieri, A.A., Guimaraes, I.G. and Santos, D.S. (1990):** Virulence factors of avian *Escherichia coli*. *Avian Diseases,* 34 (1990), pp. 531-538.
- xlvi. **Von Baum H. and Marre, R. (2005):** Antimicrobial resistance of *Escherichia coli* and therapeutic implications. *Int J Med Microbiol.* 2005;295:503–511.
- xlv. **Wen-jie, J., Zhi-ming, Z., Yong-zhi, Z., Ai-jian, Q., Hong-xia, S., Yue-long, L., Jiao, W. and Qian-qian, W. (2008):** Distribution of Virulence-Associated Genes of Avian Pathogenic *Escherichia coli* Isolates in China. *Agricultural Sciences in China* 7(12):1511-1515.
- xlv. **Wyatt, B., Steven, R., Mog, 2. and Frederick, J. (2003):** Pathogenicity and Immune Response Measured in Mice following Intranasal Challenge with Enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* Strains H10407 and B7A. *Infect Immun.* 2003 Jan; 71(1): 13–21.
- xlvi. **Yaguchi, K.; Ogitani, T.; Osawa, R.; Kawano, M.; Kokumai, N.; Kaneshige, T.; Noro, T.; Masubuchi, K. and Shimizu, Y. (2007):** Virulence factor of avian pathogenic *Escherichia coli* strains isolated from chickens with colisepticemia in Japan. *Avian Dis.* 51(3):656-662.
- xlvii. **Zhao, L., GAO, S., HUNAN, H., Xu, x., Zhu, x., Yang, w., Gao, Q., and Liu, x. (2009):** Comparison of virulence factors and expression of specific genes between uropathogenic *Escherichia coli* and avian pathogenic *E. coli* in a murine urinary tract infection model and chicken challenge model. *Microbiology-Sgm,* 155: 1634-1644.
- xlviii. **Zehor, H., Nabil, M. and Lyes, M. (2017):** Serogrouping and antibiotic resistance of *Escherichia coli* isolated from broiler chicken with colibacillosis in center of Algeria 2017. *Vet World.,* 10(7): 830–835.